

**The validity of *Bulbocerambyx* Lazarev, 2019
(Coleoptera, Cerambycidae, Cerambycini)**

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Abstract: The compositions of *Neocerambyx* J. Thomson, 1861 and *Massicus* Pascoe, 1867 are discussed. *Bulbocerambyx* Lazarev, 2019 is restored as valid.

Miroshnikov (2020) hastily proposed new synonymy: *Neocerambyx* J. Thomson, 1861 = *Bulbocerambyx* Lazarev, 2019. According to Lazarev (2019), the base for the separation of *Bulbocerambyx* (type species: *Neocerambyx grandis* Gahan 1891) was the structure of 3rd male antennal joint, which is strongly swollen in all 4 species of the genus. All other species of *Neocerambyx* and *Massicus* (sensu Miroshnikov, 2020) have more or less elongated 3rd male antennal joint, that was the reason for Lazarev (2019) to join both genera and proposed new synonymy: *Neocerambyx* J. Thomson, 1861 = *Massicus* Pascoe, 1867. Traditionally the separation of these two genera was a subject of contradictions in the scientific community. For example *Neocerambyx dierli* (Heyrovský, 1976) sensu Miroshnikov (2020), was originally described as *Massicus*, and treated as *Massicus* by Weigel (2006). *Neocerambyx philippensis* (Hüdepohl, 1990a) sensu Miroshnikov (2020) was originally described as *Massicus*. *Neocerambyx subregularis* (Schwarzer, 1931), sensu Miroshnikov (2020), was originally described as *Massicus*. *Neocerambyx unicolor* (Gahan, 1906), sensu Miroshnikov (2020), was also originally described as *Massicus*, and treated as *Massicus* by Aurivillius (1912), Hüdepohl (1994), Mitra et al. (2017), Kariyanna et al. (2017). *Neocerambyx raddei* Blessig, 1872 was treated as *Massicus* by Niisato (2007), Nga et al. (2014),

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Lim et al. (2014), Cao et al. (2015) and Kaga et al. (2018). From other side *Massicus intricatus* (Pascoe, 1866), sensu Hüdopohl (1990b) followed by Miroshnikov (2020) was originally described as *Neocerambyx*, and treated as *Neocerambyx* by Gemminger, Harold (1872) and Aurivillius (1912).

Miroshnikov (2017) himself accepted: “*Massicus* is very similar to *Neocerambyx* J. Thomson, 1861, but the diagnoses of both genera require a further detailed development, since the morphological differences between them as proposed by various researchers are generally unstable and can be used only for part of the species. *Neocerambyx* or *Massicus* (= *Mallambyx* Bates, 1873) *raddei* Blessig, 1872 can be mentioned as a striking example, when many publications treat the same species in different genera”.

Now Miroshnikov (2020) separated two genera actually on the base of a single character - the size and shape of anterior coxal cavities and corresponding lateral appendages of anterior coxae. Triangular lateral coxal appendage in *Massicus* is small and narrow, while in *Neocerambyx* much shorter. In fact the size and shape of this structure is different in different species of *Massicus* (sensu Miroshnikov) and *Neocerambyx* (sensu Miroshnikov), but it seems, the biggest coxal cavity in Miroshnikov’s *Massicus* is really smaller than smallest cavity in his *Neocerambyx*.

Unfortunately such a system is not quite applicable to all species. *Massicus philippensis* Hüdopohl, 1990a and *Massicus subregularis* Schwarzer, 1931 were not attributed by Miroshnikov (2020) to *Massicus*, neither *Neocerambyx*. And generally all corresponding species are so different that the group definitely requires a separation of more genera. That is why several more or less distinct groups of species (without subgenus rank) were delimited by Miroshnikov (2020). Some of them could be described as new genera.

All species originally included in *Bulbocerambyx* Lazarev, 2019 were accepted by Miroshnikov (2020) as *Neocerambyx* in “*paris-group*” with the exception of *Bulbocerambyx vitalisi* (Pic, 1923), which was placed by him in “*unicolor-group*”.

The statement by Miroshnikov (2020: 80, without corresponding illustrations), that *Neocerambyx unicolor* “is very

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similar to *Bulbocerambyx vitalisi*, including the structure of these antennomeres” was out of the reality. In fact 3rd antennal joint in *N. unicolor*, which can be seen in the holotype male of *Massicus vonroseni* Tippmann, 1949 (a synonym of *Neocerambyx unicolor*) depicted by Lingafelter et al. (2014), is long and narrow slightly widened apically. While 3rd antennal joint in *Bulbocerambyx vitalisi* is strongly swollen near apex.

After all I am ready to accept preliminary the high taxonomy value of the structure of anterior coxae and accept the restoration of the validity of *Massicus* Pascoe, 1867. The shape of 3rd antennal joint is also rather valuable and the genus *Bulbocerambyx* Lazarev, 2019 **nom. rest.** is quite real.

Besides the idle speculations by Miroshnikov (2020) on the similarity of *Neocerambyx vitalisi* Pic, 1923 and *Neocerambyx elenae* Lazarev, 2019 was based on nothing. *N. elenae* is a very good species not close to any other.

So, now the composition of three genera looks as:

genus *Bulbocerambyx* Lazarev, 2019, nom. rest. (type species

Neocerambyx grandis Gahan 1891)

gigas Thomson, 1878 (*Pachidissus*)

grandis Gahan, 1891 (*Neocerambyx*)

katarinae Holzschuh, 2009 (*Neocerambyx*)

vitalisi Pic, 1923 (*Neocerambyx*)

genus *Massicus* Pascoe, 1867 [RN] (type species *Cerambyx pascoei*

J. Thomson, 1857)

Conothorax J. Thomson, 1864: 230 [HN] type species *Cerambyx pascoei*

J. Thomson, 1857

Falsomassicus Pic, 1946: 7 type species *Falsomassicus theresae* Pic, 1946

***pascoei*-group by Miroshnikov (2020)**

ivani Miroshnikov, 2017

pascoei Thomson, 1857 (*Cerambyx*)

regius Miroshnikov, 2019

taiwanus Makihara & Niisato, 2014 (not fully consistent to the group)

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trilineatus Pic, 1933 (*Dymasius*) (not fully consistent to the group)
fasciatus Matsushita, 1933 (*Mallambyx*)
valentinae Miroshnikov, 2019

***fryi*-group by Miroshnikov (2020)**

fryi Gahan, 1890
scapulatus Hüdepohl, 1994

***intricatus*-group by Miroshnikov (2020)**

intricatus Pascoe, 1866 (*Neocerambyx*)
punctulipennis Holzschuh, 2018
sufficiens Holzschuh, 2018
suffusus Gressitt & Rondon, 1970

***venustus* - group by Miroshnikov (2020)**

venustus Pascoe, 1859 (*Cerambyx*)

genus *Neocerambyx* J. Thomson, 1861 (type species *Cerambyx*

paris Wiedemann, 1821)

Mallambyx Bates, 1873: 152 type species *Mallambyx japonicus* Bates, 1873
(= *Neocerambyx raddei* Blessig, 1872)

***paris*-group by Miroshnikov (2020)**

luzonicus Hüdepohl, 1987
ssp. *luzonicus* Hüdepohl, 1987
ssp. *pseudoparis* Hüdepohl, 1990
opulentus Holzschuh, 1998
paris Wiedemann, 1821: 167 (*Cerambyx*)

***unicolor*-group by Miroshnikov (2020)**

elenae Lazarev, 2019
unicolor Gahan, 1906 (*Massicus*)
vitalisi Pic, 1923

***pubescens*-group by Miroshnikov (2020)**

pubescens Fisher, 1936

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raddei-group by Miroshnikov (2020)

raddei Blessig, 1872

japonicus Bates, 1873: 152 (*Mallambyx*)

pellitus-group by Miroshnikov (2020)

bakboensis Miroshnikov, 2018

pellitus Itzinger, 1943 (*Mesocerambyx*)

rugicollis Gressitt, 1948 (*Trachylohus*)

theresae Pic, 1946 (*Falsomassicus*)

dierli-group by Miroshnikov (2020)

dierli Heyrovský, 1976 (*Massicus*)

atratus Holzschuh, 2018 (*Massicus*)

The generic position of *Massicus philippensis* Hüdepohl, 1990 and *Massicus subregularis* Schwarzer, 1931 was not stated by Miroshnikov (2020).

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